

The Influence of Inclusion in the Relationship between Workplace Diversity and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

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Abstract: The objective of this study was to identify the influence of inclusion in the relationship between workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior. Data were gathered from hospitality sector employees of Zhenjiang, city, China. The used applied a structural equation modeling (SEM) using non-probability (convenience sampling) on a sample of 252 employees to identify their gender, age and education diversity through work group involvement, influence in decision making, access to communications and resources with organizational citizenship behavior. The output of the study showed that workplace positively and significantly influenced organizational citizenship behavior. Results also showed that inclusion positively and significantly partially mediates in the relationship workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior.

Keywords: workplace diversity, inclusion, organizational citizenship behavior, hospitality sector, China

I. Introduction

Today's world is a global village, because of which firms are becoming increasingly diverse. Human resource is a sustainable competitive edge of any firm. Companies must be able to attract, keep, promote and grow high-potential workers from diverse gender, cultural and ethnic backgrounds to succeed in the world economy. Today the challenges faced by the executives of the corporation are to follow a culture that gives value to diversity and improves the potential of the entire workforce. A diverse workforce is created by workers of different demographics, cultures, religions, and religion. Diverse people have different behavior patterns. It is essential for firms to acknowledge and handle all the differences accurately. Diversity is a well-known issue in some corporations, in which staff often gets discriminated because of their diverse traits. It is also important for companies to manage their diverse employees for the best result.

Workforce diversity is a concept that was non-existent in the intellectual discussion for a long time (Duppler & Garbers, 2012). Its roots are associated with the social, financial and political forces happening around the globe (Developed countries, European countries and Asian countries) (Kaise & Prange, 2004; Phillips, 2012; Stuber, 2007). The idea of workplace diversity has been introduced in these countries with a focus on the legal protection of human traits such as age, gender, ethnicity and other characters such as physical abilities, religious practices and gender issues (Kruse & Tuck, 2011; Srivalli & Rajesh, 2013).

Barak (2016) characterized workforce diversity as recognizing, understanding, tolerating, esteeming and celebrating dissimilarities among individuals regarding an entire range of dissimilarities like age, class, ethnicity, sex, physical and intellectual capacity, race, monetary status, gender and religion. Barak (2016) additionally expressed that worker dissimilarities may be expanded to the values, organizational roles, professional and behavioral styles. Gomez and Bernet (2019) explained that diversity improves worker performance. It results in higher revenues and many other financial rewards such as innovation, increased productivity and improved accuracy. They suggest that future research should provide more accurate evaluations of how much and what kind of diversity has the most positive effects on performance and health outcomes. Improvements in personal productivity, team communication, and employees' retention can contribute to enhance both financial and clinical outcomes.

Recent research distinguished surface-level diversity from deep level diversity. Surface level diversity is directly and easily noticeable in groups (such as race, age and gender etc.) whereas the characteristics of deep-level diversity (attitudes, opinions, information, and values) become known only over time through verbal and nonverbal communication (Harrison, Price, Gavin, & Florey, 2002;). Surface level diversity is easy to measure as compare to deep level diversity. In our research we are using surface level characteristics like age, gender, education etc.

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is an employee's discretionary behavior that improves a company's efficiency, without really affecting the productivity of that individual. The most studied factors in human resource

management are the behavior of organizational citizenship (OCB) (Paine & Organ, 2000; Podsakoff et al., 2000; Purcell et al., 2009). Organ et al. (2006) characterized OCB as "employee conduct that is advantageous to the corporate, is optional and not specifically or clearly documented as the official reward system; is fairly a matter of individual choice, such that its oversight isn't punishable". OCB is supporting colleagues, improves the organization, comes before duty schedules and stays even after work hours, to help in the smooth functioning of the business; none of which is a basic requirement for the working environment (Organ et al., 2006; Podsakoff et al., 2000; Zur et al., 2012). Studies have shown that OCB improves business skills by enhancing efficiency, improving service quality, growing customer satisfaction or decreasing customer complaints (Podsakoff et al., 2000).

A lot of research has been done on the effects of diversity on organizational outcomes (Groeneveld, 2011; Mamman, Kamoche, & Bakuwa, 2012; Barak, 2013) and the relationship between diverse workforce and inclusion is studied by many researchers (Tang, Zheng, & Chen, 2017; Tang et al. 2015) but there are limited studies on the effect of inclusion on organizational citizenship behavior when the workforce is diverse (Shore et al., 2011; Wayne, Shore, & Liden, 1997). Previous researches show that the organizations with a diverse workforce have an advantage of multiple ideas in problem-solving at work, which ultimately improves the organizational performance. Organizations must create chances for workforce to work with other employees who have different expertise and views. When employees feel that they are the most significant part of their corporation, this feeling increases the morale of every employee and encourages positivity at the workplace (April, Katoma, & Peters, 2009). Muchiri and Ayoko (2013) explained that demographic diversity has an effect on organizational citizenship behaviors, affective commitment, collective efficacy and general productivity.

Moreover, previous studies propose that impact of diversity is depending on firm setting and on the type of diversity itself. Thus, we have to separate each set of diversity like age, gender and education and examine it within the specific organizational settings to completely understand the effects of diversity. In addition, the current research extends the work of Muchiri and Ayoko (2013) by taking inclusion as mediator. It is emphasized in the literature that diversity needs commitment. Individuals don't only require being unique, but they should be completely included and feel that they are important for their organization (Dehaze, 2018). Also, a worker's feeling of incorporation and climate for diversity has been found to impact the quality of work and commitment towards work (Glisson & James, 2002; Hwang & Hopkins, 2012).

II. Hypotheses Development

Workplace Diversity and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

The term "diversity" has turned out to be synonymous with the workforce diversity and with an aim of remaining in competition; companies require to gain the benefit of diversity. Diversity is the difference of individuals' societal and cultural features among individual, living collectively in an environment such as work or school (Harris et al., 2007). Diversity includes all sorts of distinctions between individuals, such as gender, age, religious affiliation, economic class, social status, marital relationships, and sexual orientation (Nelson, 2001). The combination of cultures, genders, lifestyles, and beliefs becomes a cause of conflict and clash. Most open-minded executives have to create a business atmosphere where differences are valued and where people can jointly do productive work (Nieuwmeijer, 2001).

Organizational citizenship behavior (OCB) is an interesting issue of research in the current era because significant changes are occurring in the working environment (García-Carbonell, Martín-Alcazar, & Sanchez-Gardey, 2014). In the present working environment, the boundaries between roles, duties, standards, company culture, impression administration strategies, and voluntary behavior are blurred as they never existed before. Past researchers have also exposed that the motivations associated with organizational citizenship behavior, for example, impression management, prosocial intentions, company concern (Rioux & Penner, 2001) and self-enhancement intentions are affecting the corporations in an unusual manner (Yun, Takeuchi, & Liu, 2007). Given that the OCB promotes productiveness, performance, and general organizational effectiveness (Lo, Ramayah, & Hui, 2006), corporations are operating enthusiastically to promote OCB amongst personnel (Bolino & Turnley, 2003).

Many scholars and experts approve that diversity can produce positive outcomes including improved creativity, better reputation, and increased profits (Barak, 2013; Groeneveld, 2011; Shore et al., 2009). Previous researches have proved the significant relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and diversity. Chattopadhyay et al. (2004) explained that a high degree of workforce diversity could result in lack of trust that ultimately results in a low level of communication and organizational citizenship behavior among different workers. González and Garazo (2006) also stated that a negative association exists between workforce diversity and OCB, although mediated by trust.

As the social categorization processes result in conflicts of interpersonal interactions, researchers argued that both bio-demographic (such as gender and race) and job-related diversity may negatively affect OCB (Choi, 2009; Liang, Shih, & Chiang, 2015). Tsui et al. (2002) stated that diversity in gender, race and age reduces the frequency of recommendations from workers for the betterment of the corporation. At the point when workers feel that they are surrounded by individuals with various backgrounds, it might be troublesome for them to create friendly

relationships. They feel hesitation in recommending better approaches for getting things done better (Paulus & Yang, 2000).

An age diversity climate is a key condition in which workers create a shared feeling of working in the direction of shared objectives, and also assume their corporation as an honest, reliable, caring, and long-term orientated. Thus, such circumstances should create a high-quality social exchange relationship among workers and the enterprise and also connected with a high degree of OCB (Wayne, Shore, & Liden, 1997).

In recent years, researchers show the association between gender diversity and organizational citizenship behavior (Ehrhart & Godfrey, 2003; Farrell & Finkelstein, 2007; Heilman & Chen, 2005). For instance, Kidder (2002) found that gender identity (gender, sexual orientation) has a significant effect on OCBs. The gender arrangements inside an organization adversely affect how the workforce shows OCBs. Therefore, visible demographic factors (like gender diversity) were negatively identified with OCBs. Muchiri and Ayoko (2013) study confirms that there is negative association of demographic diversity and organizational citizenship behaviors. On the basis of above discussion, the following hypothesis has been derived. Moreover, Bizri (2018) empirically confirmed that the effective commitment to the organization and employees work engagement has been positively affected by diversity management, which results in positive effect on worker's OCB. Thus we proposed the following hypotheses;

H1. Workplace diversity has a positive and significant influence on organizational citizenship behavior.

III. Workplace Diversity and Inclusion

Diversity is a double-edged sword that takes benefits, such as knowledge sharing, and also has certain drawbacks, such as conflicts or disagreements among the diverse workforce (Kulkarni, 2015), so conflicts and disputes are inevitable and even cause high cost. Recent research is shifting the focus of diversity issues into inclusion management to reduce the bad side of diversity in the work environment (Tang et al., 2015). Management of inclusion describes a series of strategies to smooth the involvement of diverse workers in their jobs. Most scholars concentrate on inclusiveness and inclusive society from a macro-level viewpoint (Trittin & Schoeneborn, 2015; Van Dijk et al., 2012). "Diversity needs dedication. Individuals need not only be different, they need to be actively involved, and they need to have their voices heard" (Dehaze, 2018).

Employment of staff to increase diversity may have a more negative effect than positive. It can cause an in-group/out-group situation in which minority groups do not feel confidence in the organization that they are secure. Supporting this, Hofhuis, Otten, and Van Der Zee (2012) expressed, "Diversity may prompt negative social procedures, for example, clashes, miscommunication, and discrimination. Therefore, especially those workers who are unique from most of their co-workers frequently encounter less job satisfaction and higher turnover rates". They argue that when inclusion strategies are practiced on diversity programs, the in-group/out-group problems are moderated and inclusion happens. These studies demonstrate that when inclusion happens there is an expansion in organizational citizenship behavior. This debate leads to the development of the following hypothesis;

H2. Workplace diversity has a positive and significant influence on inclusion.

IV. Inclusion and Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Roberson (2006) suggest inclusion as a sense of belonging, a sense of honor and respect for your identity a sense of encouragement and engagement from others in order to do the best you can do in your work. Inclusion is a change in the organizational culture and is a process that communicates with each employee and makes him or her feel valued for the organization's achievement. People feel part of the mission of the organization, perform with full potential and provide their discretionary effort when needed (April, Katoma, & Peters, 2009). The inclusive culture has result in high performing organizations where motivation exists. Similarly, Davidson and Ferdman (2002) proposed that employees be able to use their individual abilities to make some improvement in the company by becoming part of the productive activity or leading a useful task. They state that workers need to be treated decently, and that they need to feel welcomed, accepted and recognized.

This is further supported by Pless and Maak (2004), who advocate the appreciation of workers for their efforts and they should be respected. Organizational inclusion practices state many organizational rules, plans, and initiatives, the purpose of which is to form an accepting, helpful, and participative atmosphere for the workers with different backgrounds (Tang, Zheng, & Chen, 2017). Hwang and Hopkins (2015) said that if employees feel that they are included in an organization that feeling of inclusiveness results in their higher levels of organizational commitment and job satisfaction. Also, high levels of employees' organizational commitment result in low intention to leave. For increasing diversity management and organizational commitment, organization needs to improve participative decision-making structures and processes and making more reachable organizational information networks. Hence, we predicted the following hypotheses;

H3. Inclusion positively and significantly influences organizational citizenship behavior.

V. Mediating of inclusion between workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior

The research shows that there is acceleration in the organizational citizenship behavior when inclusion occurs. Inclusion is implicitly connected to improved job performance and enhanced organizational citizenship behavior (Wayne, Shore, & Liden, 1997). In this research, inclusion is used as a mediator because the study has mentioned that increased representation of diversity in an organization will lead to more adverse effects. It can create a situation in-group / out-group in which minority groups do not feel secure in the company. When companies actively manage the differences between the workers by encouraging inclusion, it increases the commonality between personnel, decreases their disagreements, and also boosts corporate performance. Brimhall, Barak, and Lizano (2014) examined the ways by which diverse organizational environment through inclusion increases job satisfaction and reduce the intention to leave. This study also demonstrates the mediating role of inclusion in the diversity of the workplace leads towards positive organizational outcomes. Perceived inclusiveness helps to keep engagement and trust, which encourages employees to react to inclusive attitudes and practices organizational citizenship and organizational commitment (Shore et al., 2011). Panicker, Agrawal, and Khandelwal (2018) stated that there is a direct and significant relationship between inclusive workplace and OCB. It has been seen that firms that have favorable environment for inclusion, a well-articulated inclusive practices and strong leaders' commitment will result in high level of OCB which shown in employees working in a higher education institution. According to the above discussion, the following hypothesis has been derived;

H4. Inclusion will positively and significantly mediate the relationship between workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior.

Conceptual Model

VI. Methodology

The nature of this study was cross-sectional and quantitative data was gathered with the help of questionnaire. The present study was focused on the employees of hospitality sector of China, province Jiangsu, and city Zhenjiang. The reason behind to collect data from hospitality sector, this is best prospect industry of the country and growing rapidly. The study applied non-probability (convenience sampling). A total 300 questionnaires were distributed among respondents and 252 questionnaires were received with proper and final response. The discard rate of the questionnaires was 48 due to improper and incomplete form of response. Table 1 shows the frequency distribution of the respondents.

Table 1. Sample Description

Demographics	Mean and Standard Deviation	Percentages
Gender		
Male 141	1.44	56.0
Female 111	.497	44.0
Age		
15-25 (72)	2.02	28.6
26-35 (114)	.818	45.2
36-45 (56)		22.2
46-above (10)		4.0
Education		
Undergraduate (186)	1.58	73.8
Masters (53)	.989	21.0
Ph.D. (13)		5.2

VII. Measures

Workplace Diversity (WPD)

Workplace diversity was measured using 21 items adapted from the previous studies of (Abbas and Hameed 2010). Workplace diversity scale had further subscales including; gender diversity, age diversity and education diversity. The Cronbach’s alpha for age diversity was 0.948; gender diversity 0.944; education diversity 0.909.

Inclusion (INC)

Inclusion was measured using 15 items scale adapted from the prior study of (Mor Barak and Cherin (1998). Inclusion scale had further subscales work group involvement, influence of decision making and access to communications and resources. The Cronbach’s alpha for all the measurement constructs were 0.937, 0.933 and 0.799 which was also the greater than threshold value 0.70.

Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB)

Organizational citizenship behavior measured using 7 items adapted from the existing study of (Yucel & Demiral, 2012). This scale was validated and accepted by previous researchers. The Cronbach’s alpha for organizational citizenship behavior was 0.949 which was considerable and accepted.

Data Analysis Techniques

The present study applied structural equation modeling SEM technique using Amos 23.0 to test of hypotheses. The benefits of using SEM provide suitable estimation of all the measurement constructs.

VIII. Measurement Model

Table 2. Cutoff Criteria

Measure	Terrible	Acceptable	Excellent
CMIN/DF	>5	>3	>1
CFI	<0.95	<0.95	>0.95
SRMR	>0.10	>0.08	<0.08
RMSEA	>0.08	>0.06	<0.06
PClose	<0.01	<0.05	>0.05

Before going to perform final analysis the study analyze measurement model test to check the fitness of the model. Therefore, the study found that CMIN 1336.960; DF 798; CMIN/DF 1.675; CFI 0.933; TLI 0.928; NFI 0.850; SRMR 0.051; RMSEA 0.052; PClose 0.259. Thus, the measurement model was fit according to the cutoff criteria values suggested by Gaskin and Kim (2016) shown in Table 2. This study also checked the composite reliability and average variance extracted (AVE) values which shown in Table 4. All the values are acceptable with the threshold values

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composite reliability greater than 0.70 and AVE greater than 0.50. Furthermore discriminant validity was assessed with the square root value of AVE and shown in Table 4 with diagonals and under diagonals values are correlations.

Figure 1. Measurement Model Fitness

Table 3. Factor Loading and Reliabilities

Variables	Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Multi-collinearity diagnostics VIF
Gender Diversity		0.948	1.090
	GED 1	.898	
	GED 2	.831	
	GED 3	.855	
	GED 4	.839	
	GED 5	.831	
	GED 6	.848	
	GED 7	.791	
	GED 8	.820	
Age Diversity	GED 9	.772	
	AGD 1	.874	1.240
	AGD 2	.900	
	AGD 3	.847	
	AGD 4	.861	

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Education Diversity		0.909	1.154
	EDD 1	.826	
	EDD 2	.797	
	EDD 3	.729	
	EDD 4	.761	
	EDD 5	.849	
	EDD 6	.775	
	EDD 7	.790	
Work Group Involvement		0.937	1.704
	WGI 1	.894	
	WGI 2	.894	
	WGI 3	.877	
	WGI 4	.840	
	WGI 5	.865	
	WGI 6	.851	
Influence in Decision Making		0.933	1.551
	IDM 1	.837	
	IDM 2	.881	
	IDM 3	.888	
	IDM 4	.815	
Access to Communications and Resources		0.799	2.205
	ACR 1	.833	
	ACR 2	.792	
	ACR 3	.645	
	ACR 4	.780	
Organizational Citizenship Behavior		0.949	
	OCB 1	.858	
	OCB 2	.834	
	OCB 3	.856	
	OCB 4	.824	
	OCB 5	.854	
	OCB 6	.893	
	OCB 7	.865	

Note: All the loading values must be greater than threshold 0.70

Table 4. Composite reliability, average variance extracted and discriminant validity

	CR	AVE	MSV	MaxR(H)	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1	0.949	0.674	0.068	0.954	0.821						
2	0.912	0.599	0.217	0.922	0.025	0.774					
3	0.937	0.713	0.217	0.943	0.082	0.466***	0.844				
4	0.910	0.590	0.106	0.912	0.128†	0.189**	0.085	0.768			
5	0.945	0.774	0.117	0.946	0.261***	0.074	0.002	0.250***	0.880		
6	0.935	0.782	0.117	0.943	0.111†	0.118†	-0.054	0.325***	0.343***	0.884	

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7	0.805	0.516	0.095	0.845	0.217**	0.099	-0.007	0.213**	0.285***	0.309***	0.718
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Note: Hu, L., Bentler, P.M. (1999),

**Values with diagonals are square root of AVE (Discriminant Validity)

*Value are below diagonals are correlations

Significance of Correlations:

† p < 0.100

* p < 0.050

** p < 0.010

*** p < 0.001

IX. Results

To test of hypotheses the study predicted H1 workplace diversity positively and negatively associated with the organizational citizenship behavior. In Table 5 results found that workplace diversity had a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior ($\beta = .331$, C.R. 3.519, p 0.01). Thus, H1 was supported. Furthermore, study predicted H2 workplace diversity has a positive influence on inclusion. The results reveal that workplace diversity had a positive and significant impact on inclusion ($\beta = .298$, C.R. 6.155, p 0.01). Therefore, H2 was accepted. Moreover, study proposed H3 inclusion has a positive effect on organizational citizenship behavior. The findings indicate that inclusion had a positive and significant effect on organizational citizenship behavior ($\beta = .402$, C.R. 3.522, p 0.01). Hence, H3 was supported. Lastly to test the mediation analysis 2000 subsample bootstrap performed on data (.). The direct effect of workplace diversity on organizational citizenship behavior was already found ($\beta = .331$, C.R. 3.519, p 0.01). After adding the mediator variable inclusion, the value of direct effect was little reduced with the addition of mediator and become ($\beta = .302$, C.R. 3.401, p 0.01) which shows the significance. The mediation analysis was shown in Table 6, whereas, indirect effect ($\beta = .120$), direct effect ($\beta = .331$) and total effect ($\beta = .451^{**}$). The lower bound value was 0.053 and upper bound value was 0.188 which shows the significance value (p= 0.01). Thus, H4 was also supported.

Table 5. Direct Effects

Relationships	Estimates	S.E.	C.R.	P	Accepted/Rejected
INC ← WPD	.298	.048	6.155	***	Accepted
OCB ← WPD	.331	.094	3.519	***	Accepted
OCB ← INC	.402	.114	3.522	***	Accepted
OCB ← WPD	.302	0.84	3.410	***	Accepted

Note: Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB); Independent Variable= Workplace Diversity (WPD); Mediator= Inclusion (INC); S.E= Standard Error; C.R= Critical Ratio; ***p<0.000

Table 6. Mediation Analysis (Indirect Effect)

Mediation Bootstrapping in testing mediator inclusion

	OCB ← WPD	INC ← WPD	OCB ← INC	Lower	Upper	Result
Direct Effect	($\beta = 0.331$) (p= 0.000)	($\beta = 0.298$) (p= 0.000)	($\beta = 0.402$) (p= 0.000)	0.053	0.188	Partial mediation
Indirect effect	($\beta = 0.120$) (p= 0.000)					
Total Effect	(0.451)*** (p= 0.000)	($\beta = 0.298$) (p= 0.000)	($\beta = 0.402$) (p= 0.000)			

Note: Dependent Variable= Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB); Independent Variable= Workplace Diversity (WPD); Mediator= Inclusion (INC); ***p<0.000

Figure 2. Path modeling

X. Discussion

The aim of this study was to investigate the influence of inclusion in the relationship between workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior among employees of hospitality sector. As we know that the workforce is becoming more diverse, so the success of any corporation depends on how well a manager manage the diverse workforce that can bring innovative ideas, perspectives and views in the workplace. H1 proposed with positive and negative association of workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior. The findings show the significance and positive impact on workplace diversity on organizational citizenship behavior. Our results are not in line with the previous studies of (Mamman, Kamoche, & Bakuwa, 2012; Mor Barak, 2013; Sacco & Schmitt, 2005; Shore et al., 2009) because in the context of Chinese culture, our study found that employees had different types of gender, age and education which changed their behaviors according to the situation as well as increase in diversity can decrease the level of trust which provide the lower interaction in workers. Thus, H1 supported to our study. Furthermore, Chattopadhyay et al. (2004) explained that increase in diversity in the organization could result in decrease in trust that ultimately results in lower level interaction and OCB amongst different workers. Moreover, Muchiri and Ayoko (2013) explained that diversity has an effect on organizational citizenship behaviors, affective commitment, collective efficacy and general productivity. Workforce diversity also results in conflicts among group members, higher turnover rate, and reduction in organizational revenues.

H2 predicted that workplace diversity has a positive association with inclusion. The findings indicate that workplace diversity had a positive and significant effect on inclusion. Therefore, our results are in consistent with the previous findings of (Tang et al., 2015) and H2 supported to the previous findings of researchers. Inclusion is associated with potential bridge which provides a vital role in the understanding of individuals regarding various backgrounds and different personal diversity traits. Inclusion could be helpful to minimize the diversity and working environment issue in the workplace of employees, it also involve in contributing the best tactics to smooth diverse employees in their work.

H3 predicted that inclusion has a positive relationship with organizational citizenship behavior. Results confirm that inclusion had a positive and significant association with organizational citizenship behavior. Thus, the present study results are in agreement with the existing studies of (Trittin & Schoeneborn, 2015; Van Dijk et al., 2012) who suggested that inclusion significantly contribute towards organizational citizenship behavior. Hence, H3 accepted and indicate the consistent findings with the prior scholars. Furthermore, recent research demonstrated that it is shifting the focus of diversity issues into inclusion management to reduce the bad side of diversity in the work environment.

H4 predicted that inclusion mediates the relationship workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior. Results reveal that inclusion partially mediates the relationship between workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior. The findings are in line with the prior researches of authors (Shore et al., 2011) who suggested the inclusion positively and significantly mediates the relationship workplace diversity and organizational citizenship behavior. Thus, H4 also confirmed the relationship between predicted variables. Furthermore, Brimhall, Barak, and Lizano (2014) explained that organizational environment of diversity through inclusion increase job satisfaction and reduce the intention to leave, providing awareness about the organizational factors that can be targeted for workplace interventions.

XI. Implications of the study

The study has some practical implications for the organizations which have diverse workforce and have a desire to improve their organizational outcomes. They need to improve manager worker relationships that can help in improving the positive perceptions of diversity. To survive in this competitive environment, organization required a stable competitive edge in the form of their human resource, but sometimes the unfair treatment of managers with

their employees and diversity among employees causes conflicts among workers which is becoming a big challenge for the organization. It is helpful for the managers that they can take initiatives to reduce the discrimination among employees by eliminating unjust system or by developing the organizational practices of equality and justice. This acknowledgement would enable the managers to develop appropriate policies towards status equalization. Managers and supervisors should work to improve their individual relationships with employees of their corporation. They can improve their relationship with their subordinates by spending time with them, by involving them in daily decision making, and by making them feel that they are a part of the organization.

XII. Limitations and Future Research Directions

Regardless of contribution of present research on practical and theoretical facets, some limitations regarding sample size and generalizability of the research exists. The future research may be carried out on the limitations of this study. Due to lack of time, the cross-sectional design of data collection is used. Future scholars can use longitudinal study that gives them a decent knowledge of the topic. Sample was collected from one city. Therefore, the results should be generalized carefully to other geographical locations. As we know some countries are more diverse and each country has different types of diversities. So, the variations in diversity among countries need to be further studied. The current study investigates only three representative dimensions of workplace diversity. However, other dimensions of workplace diversity also exist like cultural diversity, ethnic diversity etc. In future, the researchers have to focus on the development and validation of the organizational inclusion scale. They may include the fair employee treatment, cooperative work arrangement, and shared information systems, etc.

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